

Exploring Media Relations: Discourse Analysis of PR-Media Conversations in Philippine Media Events

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Abstract

Background: Media events serve as spaces where public relations specialists and members of the media mutually benefit from one another. In these settings, conversations are shared, relationships are established and maintained.

Objective of the Study: This study examines the conversations exchanged between public relations specialists and media members, which constitute the language of media relations in media events.

Methodology: Adopting a qualitative approach, six audio recordings of conversations were used as the study's corpus. These recordings took place in various settings and at different times, involving different participants to ensure data triangulation. Conversations during a press conference, a protest action, and a degustation event were recorded. The

recordings were transcribed and analysed using two approaches to discourse analysis in communication: Ethnography of Communication and Conversation Analysis.

Results: The findings revealed that each type of media event requires a specific tone to maintain effective conversation. Periods of silence can lead to awkwardness or tension within the group, which can be alleviated through the initiation of small talk. Social capital functions as the guiding norm of interaction in media events, where conversations are generally smooth in terms of turn-taking and adjacency. Regardless of the type of media event, all participants engage in conversation with the aim of fulfilling their objectives for attending the event.

Unique Contribution: By focusing on the conversations shared between PR specialists and media members, this study serves as a foundation for further exploration of discourse in media events, addressing a gap in discourse studies on media relations.

Conclusion: Reciprocation of compliments, reliance on information, and shared interests drive conversations in media events.

Key Recommendation: This study examines the verbal aspects of media relations in media events. It is recommended that future research explore the non-verbal cues exhibited by PR specialists and media members to broaden and deepen the understanding of media relations.

Key words: media relations, media events, conversation analysis, ethnography of communication, discourse analysis

Introduction

Every organisation requires a public relations (PR) department, whether in-house or outsourced, to manage its brand and reputation and effectively communicate its message to the general public, particularly customers and investors (Wilson & Sern, 2019).

Media relations, a key PR function, fosters a harmonious relationship with members of the media who may be interested in featuring a client's product, service, or event. Through conversations, maintaining a strong relationship between PR specialists and media professionals benefits both parties. Media professionals spend less time searching for story sources and verifying information, while PR specialists secure free publicity and promotion for their clients without resorting to advertorials. However, according to Lloyd and Toogood (2015, as cited in Cavaco, 2023), this dynamic suggests that journalists rely on PR specialists more than the latter depend on them, particularly in an era where people are increasingly reluctant to pay for access to information.

As various media professionals attend different types of media events, it is the responsibility of PR specialists to engage in face-to-face conversations with them, regardless of whether they have met before. According to Poursamimi et al. (2021), conversations are a form of spoken language that can occur in any setting with the purpose of establishing and maintaining social ties. This interaction enables both the media and the company to benefit from effective media relations. Fetig (2004, as cited by Supa and Zoch, 2009) highlights that PR specialists tend to trust reporters they are familiar with while being wary of those they do not know. Mutual trust serves as the foundation of relationships between PR specialists and media professionals.

In this context, a communication gap between PR specialists and new media professionals is apparent, as the challenge of building trust persists before and during their face-to-face encounters. Furthermore, new media professionals may find it difficult to collaborate regularly with PR specialists, as the latter often exhibit a preference for media professionals they already know.

This study addresses this gap by examining the language of media relations in media events. Specifically, it explores the discursive patterns present in media event conversations, where relationships between PR specialists and media professionals are established and maintained. The aim is to enhance participants' awareness of interaction norms and the structure of conversations—how they begin, progress, and conclude—during face-to-face interactions. This research will assist aspiring PR specialists and media professionals in understanding how relationships are built and sustained in media events through language, helping to prevent tension and discomfort while facilitating a smooth and natural flow of communication. Given the scarcity of discourse studies on media events, not only in the Philippines but globally, this study seeks to initiate an exploration of discourse in media event settings.

Objectives of the Study

With the lack of research on discourses in media events, it is essential to examine the language of media relations in these settings. This study aims to:

- Determine how media relations take place using the following parameters: setting, participants, ends, act sequence, key, instrumentalities, norms of interaction, and genre; and
- Discuss discursive patterns in conversations through participants' utterances and transitions.

Framework of the Study

This study employed two approaches to discourse analysis: Ethnography of Communication and Conversation Analysis (CA). The researcher developed the operational framework to illustrate the discourse that constitutes the language of media relations as it occurs in media events.

Figure 1. Operational Framework

Methodology

Research Design

The study adopted a qualitative approach. According to Jang and Sung (2024), communication gaps and challenges can be effectively addressed through qualitative research. This method is essential for identifying patterns in conversations between PR specialists and media professionals in the process of building and maintaining relationships.

Corpus of the Study

The researcher recorded conversations between PR specialists and media professionals in three different types of media events, ensuring data triangulation: a press conference, a protest, and a degustation. These events took place at different times, locations, and settings, involving different participants. A total of six recordings were used as the study's corpus, with two recordings for each type of media event. Lemon and Hayes (2020) argue that data triangulation minimises bias in analysis and interpretation, enhances the validity

of results, and reduces the risk of false conclusions. An MP3 recorder was used to capture the conversations, which primarily involved PR specialists and media professionals. The recordings were transcribed using the Jeffersonian Notation System for Conversation Analysis (CA).

Ethical Considerations

The researcher sought permission from the head of a PR company to record media event conversations one month prior to the commencement of the first event. A formal letter of request was sent, which was duly acknowledged and signed by the PR company's head. To ensure minimal intrusion, only audio recordings were made. Participants were informed about the recordings after their conversations, and they granted verbal consent for their use strictly for academic and research purposes. Furthermore, pseudonyms were assigned to protect the identities of participants, concealing their names as well as the organisations or publications they were affiliated with.

Research Procedure

The recorded conversations were analysed in two stages: (1) Ethnography of Communication and (2) Conversation Analysis.

S *setting*: where the speech event is located in time and space
P *participants*: who takes part in the speech event, and in what role (e.g. speaker, addressee, audience, eavesdropper)
E *ends*: what the purpose of the speech event is, and what its outcome is meant to be
A *act sequence*: what speech acts make up the speech event and what order they are performed in
K *key*: the tone or manner of performance (serious or joking, sincere or ironic, etc.)
I *instrumentalities*: what channel or medium of communication is used (e.g. speaking, singing, writing, drumming, whistling) and what language/variety is selected from the participants' repertoire
N *norms of interaction*: what the rules are for producing and interpreting speech acts
G *genres*: what 'type' does a speech event belong to, and what other pre-existing conventional forms of speech are drawn on or 'cited' in producing appropriate contributions to talk (e.g. do people quote from mythology or poetry or scripture?)

Figure 2. Hymes' SPEAKING GRID

Stage 1: Ethnography of Communication. This stage enabled the description of social and communicative behaviour in media relations. Using Hymes' SPEAKING Grid, the rules of speaking in media events were examined. Figure 2 above presents a description of this grid, originally developed by Hymes (1972, as cited in Limgomolvilas & Wudthayagorn, 2022).

Stage 2: Conversation Analysis. To further examine discourse features not observed in Stage 1, Conversation Analysis (CA) was employed. This method identifies how participants in a conversation understand and respond to one another through turn-taking, adjacency pairs, and overlaps (Cameron, 2001).

Results and Discussion

1. Research Objective 1: Determine how media relations take place using the following parameters: setting, participants, ends, act sequence, key, instrumentalities, norms of interaction, and genre.

Setting

Press Conference

The Bayleaf Intramuros is a luxury hotel located in Intramuros, one of the oldest and most historic districts in Manila. The press conference took place in function rooms Muralla 2 and 3, which have a seating capacity of 150. The room was equipped with air-conditioning, a surround sound system, and LCD projectors. The temperature ranged from 20 to 25 degrees Celsius, with standard lighting settings. No noticeable interruptions occurred during the conversation.

Protest Action

The protest took place along the coastal shore of Harbour Square Manila. The venue was large enough to accommodate a stage, a sound system, a mini banca (displayed for photography), and 100 seats, all arranged for the media event. The temperature was around 25 to 30 degrees Celsius. Stage lighting was set up but was not distracting to the conversation. Despite loud music playing from the speakers while waiting for the event to begin, no interruptions in the conversations were observed.

Degustation

The degustation event was held in a function room at Romulo Café – Makati. The event aimed to showcase Filipino cuisine prepared by Romulo Café. It was an exclusive gathering, with only select media members invited to cover the occasion. The air-conditioned room was spacious enough to accommodate all attendees. The event was scheduled to begin at 7 PM, with invited media members asked to arrive an hour earlier to ensure they would not miss any part of the programme. All attendees were assigned seating arrangements, while PR specialists sat at a table with media members.

All the locations where these media events took place were considered suitable for participants. According to Olariu and Nichifor (2015), venues should be accessible, well-

ventilated, spacious, and equipped with good acoustics to ensure clear communication and a professional atmosphere.

Participants

Participants in media events primarily consist of clients, stakeholders, PR specialists, and media professionals. Regardless of whether a PR specialist and a media member are acquainted, media events serve as platforms for relationship-building and maintenance. A similar observation was made by Chukwu (2023), who stated that face-to-face interactions in media events establish meaningful relationships and foster a sense of community. This, in turn, increases the likelihood of both PR specialists and media members achieving their media objectives.

Ends

Regardless of the type of media event, participants attended for two primary reasons: (1) media professionals covered the event to take photographs or write articles and (2) PR specialists ensured that media professionals gathered all the necessary information to achieve desired publicity. However, the way conversations ended varied depending on the type of media event. In press conferences and protests, conversations were often cut short by journalists, who prioritised data gathering over relationship-building. These media events are news-driven, as they provide newsworthy content (Gans, 2004). In degustation events, conversations prioritised relationship-building over data gathering. Since these events are PR-driven, the objective was to generate favourable media coverage (Waters et al., 2010).

Act Sequence

Common patterns in media event conversations included (1) initial greetings, signalling potential interaction; (2) small talk, which facilitated rapport-building; (3) discussion of media kits, initiated by either PR specialists or media professionals; and (4) conversations ending abruptly through cut-offs, usually dictated by either the client or media professionals. According to Reyaz and Tripathi (2016), analysing the talk sequence within a speech community provides insights into the social and cultural aspects of interaction. The structured nature of PR-media conversations in Philippine media events reflects these patterns.

Keys

The tone of voice and interaction style varied depending on the type of media event: press conferences and degustation events featured flattery and humour, while protest actions were more formal in tone. Small talk and laughter often transitioned conversations from formal to casual. Fasbinder (2022, as cited in Haddad, 2024) described tone of voice as not

only influencing perceptions of a speaker but also increasing the listener's engagement. Adjusting tone and interaction style according to the type of media event enhances the quality and quantity of shared information.

Instrumentalities

All participants engaged in verbal communication, primarily using “TagLish”—a mix of Tagalog and English. According to Reyes (2017), TagLish is a linguistic hybrid that reflects the desire to be modern while maintaining familiarity and comfort in conversation. This language mixing ensures ease of communication, allowing participants to build and maintain relationships.

Norms of Interaction

Social capital played a crucial role in Philippine media events, allowing participants to expand their networks and build trust. The type of social capital used depended on the nature of the event: (1) in press conferences, interactions often involved reciprocation of compliments; (2) in protest actions, there was a stronger reliance on factual information; and (3) in degustation events, conversations were driven by familiarity and shared interests. These findings support Willis' (2012) argument that social capital is fostered through the sharing of norms in face-to-face interactions. This dynamic in Philippine media events helps sustain relationships between PR specialists and media professionals.

Genre

Regardless of whether conversations were formal or humorous, small talk played a central role in media event interactions. According to Umar et al. (2024), small talk is prevalent in workplace communication. This suggests that conversations in Philippine media events are largely structured around small talk, as it helps PR specialists and media professionals establish and maintain relationships.

2. Research Objective 2: Discuss discursive patterns in conversations through participants' utterances and transitions

Turn-taking Patterns

Turn-taking indicates that one speaker speaks at a time. The conversation is considered smooth if the speakers wait for each other to finish talking (Okeke & van der Westhuizen, 2020). On the other hand, failure to achieve a smooth transition is mostly caused by overlaps. According to Cameron (2001), these disruptions affect how the new speaker properly responds to the previous speaker's utterance.

Press Conference

Table 1. Frequency of turns and speech overlap per participant (Press Conference)

PARTICIPANTS	TURNS	OVERLAPS
<i>Recording 1</i>		
PR specialist	14	2
Writer	14	2
<i>Recording 2</i>		
PR specialist	14	3
Writer	15	3
TOTAL	57	10

Focusing on conversations where one speaker listens while the other is speaking, interactions in a press conference were relatively smooth due to the nearly balanced distribution of turns and the minimal number of overlaps recorded, as presented in Table 1. Cameron (2001) stated that genuine and meaningful interaction is ensured when there is proper coordination in the exchange between participants. Observing appropriate turn-taking is therefore essential in conversations during press conferences.

Protest Action

Table 2. Frequency of turns and speech overlap per participant (Protest Action)

PARTICIPANTS	TURNS	OVERLAPS
<i>Recording 1</i>		
PR specialist	14	2
Photographer	15	3
<i>Recording 2</i>		
PR specialist	15	2
Reporter	13	5
TOTAL	57	12

Table 2 shows that self-selection in protest action was observed immediately after the current speaker had finished, indicating a smooth flow of conversation with a well-distributed number of turns. Cameron (2001) stated that self-selection promotes equal opportunities for both participants in the conversation to take the speaking floor. This is particularly essential in media events to ensure respect and understanding in conversations,

which in turn helps to build and maintain relationships. On the other hand, the writer recorded 13 turns with five overlaps. A lack of coordination was observed due to the overlaps. According to Cameron (2001), these are disruptions that affect the way the new speaker properly responds to the previous speaker’s utterance. This highlights the importance of waiting for one’s turn to speak in order to avoid overlaps and maintain a smooth flow of conversation in protest-action events.

Degustation

Table 3. Frequency of turns and speech overlap per participant (Degustation)

PARTICIPANTS	TURNS	OVERLAPS
<i>Recording 1</i>		
PR specialist	28	7
Writer	25	5
Client	1	1
<i>Recording 2</i>		
PR specialist	34	7
Writer	29	5
Client	1	1
TOTAL	54	13

In Table 3, the conversations during the degustation were dominated by the PR specialists, resulting in a relatively smooth flow of conversation. This was evident from the number of turns taken, with minimal overlaps recorded. The client, who had an overlapping turn, marked the end of the conversation by introducing another writer for the PR specialist to engage with. According to Delli et al. (2022), cut-offs are usually followed by a self-repair segment that addresses an issue in the current speaker’s utterance. However, in degustation conversations, the cut-off serves as a reminder for the PR specialist to return to the primary objective of media relations—meeting and greeting every media member attending the event. This is crucial, as failing to acknowledge a media member may lead to misunderstandings or misinterpretations of the PR specialist’s actions.

Adjacency Pairs and Overlaps

Yao et al. (2024) stated that adjacency pairs are a common structure identified in conversation analysis. These are pairs of utterances in which the second utterance is required as a response to the first. Both utterances must be adjacent, related to each other, and produced by different speakers.

Press Conference

1	P1:	<i>Hi, Jea::n [£Long time no see:]</i>
2	P2:	<i>[Hi:: Ang ganda mo ↑ngayon ha]</i>
3	P1:	<i>Thank you (0.3) Ikaw di:n you're looking good ↑ha</i>
4	P2:	<i>Ay nako naman heh heh heh binola mo pa ko (0.6) By the way, this is ↑John (0.3) our PR associate (0.5) [you can] look for him whenever you need something okay?</i>
5	P1:	<i>[Hi John] (1.6) Alright</i>
Translation:		
1	P1:	Hi, Jean. Long time no see.
2	P2:	Hi. You're looking pretty today.
3	P1:	Thank you. You're looking good, too.
4	P2:	Oh my! Stop patronizing me. By the way, this is John, our PR associate. You can look for him whenever you need something, okay?
5	P1:	Hi, John. Alright.

In the excerpt above, the writer greeted the PR specialist (Line 1), which was overlapped by another greeting from the latter (Line 2). The overlapping utterance was adjacent to the first, as it was a direct response to the initial greeting. Furthermore, the writer thanked the PR specialist (Line 3) in response to the overlapping utterance made by the latter (Line 2), making it adjacent as well. A similar scenario was observed when the writer's overlap (Line 5) acknowledged John in response to the introduction made by the PR specialist (Line 4). These observations indicate that the overlaps did not disrupt the flow of conversation but rather demonstrated mutual interest in engaging, as the participants were already familiar with each other. Tannen (2005) stated that some overlaps are more cooperative than disruptive; participants may speak simultaneously to express enthusiasm, agreement, or engagement, thereby enhancing conversational flow.

Protest Action

Most adjacency pairs took the form of explanation-clarification. As shown in the excerpt below, the PR specialist explained how the picture-taking would proceed (Lines 17 and 19), while the field reporter's utterances served as clarifications through questions. Both participants engaged in self-selection, which sustained the conversation. However, this led to some overlaps from the field reporter, recorded in Lines 18 and 20, as they spoke while the PR specialist was still talking. Since both participants engaged in self-selection, interruptions were not solely attributed to the field reporter; the PR specialist also recorded an interruption, as seen in Line 21. This cooperative dynamic aligns with Schegloff's (2007) argument that adjacency pairs demonstrate collaboration between conversation participants, depending on how responses align with expectations. In this case, the explanation-clarification pairs illustrate that both the PR specialist and the field reporter were interacting with the primary objective of effectively covering the event.

- 17 P2: Pag-float ng ganon (0.3) may formation yung dragon boat Yacht Club (0.5) with all these streamers, uniform streamers containing that message (2.5) tapos (0.5) yung second photo (0.4) yung bawa pag 7 o'clock >wala nang dragon boat so less: (0.5) less [elements yan]
- 18 P1: [Ah.: Di na kumpleto?]
- 19 P2: Oo: (1.0) ang hindi kasi natin nakuha yung permit from: (0.3) DENR tsaka LGU (0.3) na pwede sana yung mga mangingisda: naka-fishing boats (0.4) pupunta don from Bacoor >so may iba ka pang photo op entry (0.5) [yung approach]
- 20 P1: [So parang iikot] ka non kase sa MOA diba? Ang laki ng=
- 21 P2: Oo pero maganda sana yung shot na yon kasi merong: salubong yon e (0.3) that's the intention:

Translation:

- 17 P2: Once floated, there will be a formation by Manila Yacht Club and Dragon Boat Team with all these uniform streamers with that message. At 7 o'clock, the Dragon Boat Team won't be there anymore for the second photo so we will have lesser elements.
- 18 P1: Incomplete?
- 19 P2: Yes. We didn't get any permit from DENR and LGU allowing fishermen to pose with their fishing boats going to Bacoor but you may still have a different photo entry focusing on the approach
- 20 P1: So, it's like you'll go around MOA, right? It's big=
- 21 P2: Yes, but that shot is more convincing since there's this passing and that's the intention

Degustation

The active use of self-selection by the participants contributed to a lack of coordination in the pairs of utterances observed in the conversation below. Both participants were attempting to take the speaking floor while another speaker was still talking. The presence of self-selection was evident in the overlaps recorded in Lines 35 and 37 by the PR specialist and Line 36 by the writer. The frequent overlaps in three consecutive utterances indicated that both participants were eager to speak during the interaction. According to Sacks et al. (1974), when participants in a conversation self-select while the current speaker is still talking, it can lead to overlaps and competition for the speaking floor, signalling a breakdown in conversational coordination. This may negatively impact the PR specialist's ability to build and maintain relationships with media members.

- 32 P1: *Talaga? Ako I got married at twenty three*
33 P2: *I got married at 19*
34 P1: *heh [heh heh heh]*
35 P2: *[But you know (.) I] used to (.) I knew what good food wa:s (0.5) but the ingredients and all that, you'll lea::rn (0.5) and so, ↑me (0.3) I was a very curious person so I talked to the chef and a::sked (.) what's thi:s, what's tha:t heh heh heh heh You know [(0.5) to] broaden you:r=*
36 P1: *[Yah::] Especially now we have a lot of original [cuisines and] it's like ahh: (0.5) we go from one place to the other you do not know*
37 P2: *[Correct]*

Translation:

- 32 P1: Really? I got married at twenty three
33 P2: I got married at nineteen
34 P1: (laughs)
35 P2: But you know, I used to... I knew what good food was but the ingredients and all that, you'll learn. And so, me, I was a very curious person so I talked to the chef and asked what's this, what's that (laughs). You know, to broaden your=
36 P1: Yah. Especially now we have a lot of original cuisines and it's like, we go from one place to the other, you do not know...
37 P2: Correct.

Conclusion

The settings of media events are organised by clients who seek publicity for their brand and organisation. The physical arrangements are designed to ensure that all attendees are comfortable and have easy access to information. Participants in media events mainly consist of clients, PR specialists, and members of the media. Others, such as support groups, advocates, and local residents, are also welcome to attend. Everyone takes the initiative to greet others upon arrival, signalling the possibility of a conversation. Participants can engage freely in discussions, often initiated by small talk to help build rapport and interest. Conversations in media events are driven by reciprocation of compliments, reliance on shared information, and familiarity with common interests. While some participants engage in casual exchanges, others focus on and follow instructions. The tone of communication and interaction in media events varies, depending on the nature of the event, and may be flattering, humorous, or formal. All participants engage in verbal communication, predominantly using “TagLish”, a blend of Tagalog and English.

Turn-taking patterns among participants in media events differ. In press conferences, turns are evenly distributed, while conversations in protest actions and degustations tend to flow

more smoothly. Some turns occur as a continuation of the current speaker's utterance, particularly during moments of silence, which can sometimes create awkwardness or tension within the group. At times, participants employ self-selection when taking turns, which may lead to minor overlaps and a few non-adjacent pairs in media relations.

Recommendations

Based on the study's findings, the following recommendations are proposed:

1. One of the key factors that contributes to successful relationship-building between PR professionals and media members is their informal, open, and casual style of communication. It is recommended that professionals in this field continue fostering this approach to enhance collaboration and achieve their relationship-building objectives.
2. Silences are an inevitable part of media interactions and may occasionally arise in conversations. It is suggested that professionals continue using small talk as a strategy to ease tension and reduce awkwardness during exchanges.
3. This study focused on the verbal aspects of media relations in media events. Future research is recommended to explore non-verbal cues used by PR specialists and media members to provide a more comprehensive understanding of media interactions.
4. The study examined three types of media events: press conferences, protest actions, and degustations. Further research is recommended to observe media relations in other types of media events (e.g. press releases, speeches, and interviews) to broaden the understanding of language use in different media settings.

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